

Analytical procedure for studying land empathy in Participatory Scenario Planning

This document supports the methodology used in a manuscript currently under review: Petrescu-Mag R. M., Petrescu D. C, Balc R. (2026). Collective care and rural transitions: The role of empathy in addressing land degradation, submitted to Sociologia Ruralis. It provides a detailed account of the analytical procedure used in the study.

All workshop discussions were audio-recorded and transcribed verbatim, then subjected to intelligent transcription. The analysis employed an Interpretive Discourse Analysis (IDA) approach, which integrates interpretive and discourse-historical principles [(Wodak, 2001; Yanow, 2000) cited by Wash (2020)]. IDA assumes that meaning is produced through language-in-use, i.e., participants do not merely describe experiences but perform emotions, values, and moral positions through speech acts (e.g., expressing commitments, making moral claims, attributing agency to nature) (Adjei, 2013; Wetherell and Potter, 1988). In this study, IDA was applied abductively and iteratively (Wash, 2020), with interpretation moving back and forth between the textual level (what was said), the contextual level (who said it, where, and why), and the theoretical level (empathy and perspective-taking). This cyclical process typically involves six interpretive stages [defining the discursive focus, building the corpus, establishing context, interpreting discourse, developing interpretive categories, and synthesizing meanings (Wash, 2020)] which, for practical purposes, are presented here in four analytical steps (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Sequential application of the four IDA analytical steps in normative scenario planning to examine pathways toward land degradation neutrality

Step 1. Defining the discursive focus, building the corpus, and establishing the theoretical lens. The first stage of the analysis involved *defining the discursive phenomenon* under investigation, namely how participants constructed moral responsibility, emotional engagement, and social belonging as they discussed land degradation and community futures. The analytical *corpus* comprised full, verbatim transcripts (subsequently processed using intelligent transcription) of the participatory workshop with local stakeholders in the Târnava Mare microregion. Although intelligent transcription was used, the transcription process was carefully reviewed and adjusted to ensure that it captured not only participants' words but also the emotional and performative aspects of their speech (e.g., pauses and hesitations, changes in tone or emphasis, identified through researchers' analytical notes and reflexive memos taken during and after the participatory sessions, or within the verbatim transcription), which are central to interpretive discourse analysis.

This approach preserved relevant pauses, tone shifts, laughter, and emphases that conveyed feelings, values, or moral positioning, while removing only non-meaningful repetitions or fillers (e.g., original intelligent transcription: "We have been working on this land for a long time and it is difficult now", adjusted transcript: "We have been working on this land for a long time [*pause*] and it is difficult *now*"). This ensured that both the semantic content and the affective dimension of speech were retained for analysis. In this way, the transcription process retained the expressive quality of participants' speech, allowing the subsequent IDA to reflect how emotions and perspectives were enacted through language rather than merely described. Moving to the last moment of this step, the study adopted four *theoretical lenses* commonly used in IDA, to establish a clear interpretive frame:

- i) *The interpretive perspective* (Yanow, 2000), which examines how participants make sense of their lived world through language;
- ii) *The discourse-historical perspective* (Wodak, 2001), situating statements within the broader socio-historical narratives, including post-communism rural transformation and environmental ethics;
- iii) *The performative view of language* (Wetherell and Potter, 1988), which conceptualizes language as action rather than description;
- iv) *The affective positioning lens* (Adjei, 2013), focusing on how empathy connects speakers.

Collectively, these four lenses guided the analytic reading of the transcript (described in Steps 2, 3, and 4), shaping how segments of talk were selected, contextualized, and interpreted. This integrated

approach ensures that meaning-making, historical positioning, performative action, and affective relations were examined simultaneously rather than in isolation.

Step 2. Establishing context and situating the data. Contextual information was systematically integrated to support interpretive validity. Consistent with the discourse-historical approach, each excerpt was located within its situational frame (who spoke, to whom, and during which phase of the workshop); relevant institutional and historical contexts, such as post-communism land reforms and regional ecological narratives; and local cultural and linguistic conventions, particularly references to Saxon heritage and land stewardship traditions. This contextual embedding ensured that interpretations reflected socially situated meaning-making rather than decontextualized linguistic patterns. Knowledge of local land-use practices, demographic shifts, and environmental challenges was used to understand the communicative work of each quote, including acknowledging responsibility, expressing empathy, and inviting cooperation. This step strengthened interpretive validity by linking discourse to its socio-ecological context.

Step 3. Interpreting discourse through identification and contextual analysis of empathy-related features. The third stage of analysis involved close textual analysis guided by the IDA principle of abductive interpretation, in which insight moves back and forth between language, context, and theory. The transcript was read multiple times to capture tone, rhythm, and interactional flow across the workshop phases (e.g., problem definition, visioning, and backcasting).

Within the identification of empathy-related discourse features, expressions known to signal empathy in prior research (El Refaie and Thatcher, 2025; Galang et al., 2025) were identified. Five key linguistic indicators were used to locate empathic, moral, or collaborative language: pronoun shifts, affective verbs, deontic constructions, metaphorical imagery, and contrastive phrasing. These indicators, adapted from prior studies, are summarized in Table 1 and served as the operational tool for identifying empathy-related discourse features across the analytical corpus.

Table 1. Linguistic indicators of empathic discourse

Linguistic feature	Illustrative examples	Analytic interpretation
Pronoun shifts	“I used to think the hill was just land, now we see it as part of us .”	Movement from individual to collective stance; indicates inclusion, shared identity, and collective responsibility.
Affective verbs and evaluative adjectives	Verbs: <i>to feel, to care, to hurt, to love</i> ; Adjectives: <i>beautiful, harsh, painful, alive</i> , e.g., “ We feel attached to this valley ”; “ The land is tired .”	Express emotional and moral evaluation of place; reveal attachment, concern, or compassion.

Modal or deontic constructions	“We must protect the soil,” “We should teach the children to plant trees”; “Let’s not forget those who depends on the forest.”	Convey obligation, shared ethical stance, and collective moral responsibility.
Metaphorical or sensory imagery	“ The land breathes again ”, “ The village has a heartbeat ”, “ You can smell the wet earth after rain ”, “ The land is tired. ”	Embodied and sensory metaphors that reflect emotional engagement, imagination, and relational thinking toward the environment and community.
Contrastive or hypothetical phrasing	“ If I were a young farmer today, I’d probably leave too”; “ If we keep cutting trees, the river will punish us later.”	Demonstrates perspective-taking, anticipation of future consequences, and reasoning from others’ viewpoints.

Each expression identified using linguistic indicators was examined in its context (speaker and workshop phase) to determine its communicative function, such as eliciting empathy, acknowledging shared responsibility, or fostering cooperation. This procedure aligns with the interpretative phase of IDA, in which textual elements are treated as carriers of implicit moral and emotional meanings rather than as neutral statements.

By combining textual and contextual analysis, empathy-related expressions were traced within interactional dynamics rather than as isolated statements. Attention was given to how discourse enacted social and moral work, revealing the iterative process through which participants co-constructed a shared sense of responsibility and care. This stage enabled the systematic operationalization of empathy within the discourse.

Step 4. Tracing discursive progression and synthesizing meanings. The fourth stage of analysis focused on the temporal progression and transformation of empathic discourse across different workshop phases. Here, the analysis examined how specific linguistic patterns evolved. For example, early self-referential statements (e.g., “I think...”) often shifted into plural, ethically oriented formulations (e.g., “we must...” or “we can...”) during subsequent visioning and backcasting discussions. This temporal tracing corresponded to IDA’s interpretive synthesis stage, emphasizing how meanings are refined, negotiated, and reconstituted through ongoing interaction. These discursive progressions were identified to document the movement from individual reflection toward collective moral alignment.

At this final stage, emergent interpretive categories (e.g., moral responsibility, empathic attachment, and tradition-based ethics) were consolidated through repeated cross-referencing between the empirical data and the theoretical lenses defined in Step 1. This iterative process ensured that the conceptual synthesis remained grounded in participants’ discourse while maintaining consistency with IDA’s abductive

reasoning approach. This step enabled the integration of empirical observations into higher-order interpretive categories.

By structuring the analysis around these four operational steps, the methodology operationalized the procedural logic of IDA, providing a transparent and replicable framework for examining how participants' language both reflected and actively constructed the emotional, moral, and relational dimensions of collective meaning-making during the workshop. Through systematic identification of linguistic indicators, contextual interpretation, and temporal tracing of empathic expressions, the analysis maintained fidelity to IDA's interpretive principles while capturing the dynamic ways in which empathy functioned as a discursive resource for community understanding and environmental responsibility.

References

- Adjei, S.B., 2013. Discourse analysis: Examining language use in context. *The Qualitative Report* 18, 1–10. <https://nsuworks.nova.edu/tqr/vol18/iss25/2>
- El Refaie, E., Thatcher, C., 2025. Becoming buttercups: fostering eco-empathy through metaphorical creative writing. *Metaphor Symb.* 40, 99–113.
- Galang, E.I.N.E., Bennett, E.M., Hickey, G., Baird, J., Dale, G., Sherren, K., 2025. Co-imagining future scenarios can enhance environmental actors' empathy toward future generations and non-human life-forms. *Sustain. Sci.* 20, 511–524.
- Wash, I., 2020. Interpreting public policy dilemmas: Discourse analytical insights. *Humanit. Soc. Sci. Commun.* 7, 1–12.
- Wetherell, M., Potter, J., 1988. Discourse analysis and the identification of interpretative repertoires. *Anal. Everyday Explan. Casebook Methods* 1688183.
- Wodak, R., 2001. The discourse-historical approach. *Methods Crit. Discourse Anal.* 1, 63–94.
- Yanow, D., 2000. *Conducting interpretive policy analysis*. 2455 Teller Road. Sage Publications, Thousand Oaks.